

PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF THE PREVALENCE OF DRUG ABUSE AND CRIME IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study was a public perception investigation into drug abuse and crime in Akwa Ibom State, South-South Zone of Nigeria. It adopted descriptive and inferential research designs to analyse the data obtained from a sample size of 1003, drawn from a population of 7,200,000 using Cochran's sampling technique, in an ordered manner to establish relationships between variables. The data collected were retrieved from questionnaires administered to the general public as well as through interviews with staff at the Correctional Centre in Uyo and Eket, while staff from the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) were interviewed in Uyo. The study posed six research questions and tested four hypotheses. It employed three theories as the theoretical framework for the research: Social Learning Theory, Strain Theory, and Rational Choice Theory. The four hypotheses were analysed using Pearson's product-moment correlation, while the interview results were subjected to thematic and content analysis, emphasising excerpts or verbatim quotes from the interviewees. The findings revealed, among other things, that there is a prevalence of drug abuse and related crimes in Akwa Ibom State and that the influence of drug abuse on crime in the state varies between men and women. The recommendations include educating Akwa Ibom State citizens about the dangers of drug abuse and its negative effects on individuals, society, and the state.

Keywords: *Drug abuse, crime, Odogoro, and illegal drug use*

Introduction

The intricate relationship between legal and illegal drug use, drug trafficking, and organised crime has garnered attention at national, regional, and international levels, leading to various strategies for drug control (NDCMP, 2019). Consequently, it is crucial to explore the connection between drug abuse and crime to understand the extent of societal harm. Goldstein's work in 1985, known as the tripartite framework, was among the initial efforts to acknowledge the complexity of the drugs-crime relationship (Sarker and Faller, 2016). This framework integrated economic motivation, systemic, and psychopharmacological models, illustrating how the inherently violent nature of the drug subculture, alongside the effects of drug intoxication and the economic pressures presumed to be linked to financing drug use, can converge to affect the initiation and variations in criminal activity (Curtis & Wendel, 2007).

In Nigeria, one in seven individuals aged 15-64 years has used a drug (excluding tobacco and alcohol) in the previous year" (UNODC, 2018). The estimated past-year prevalence of any drug use stands at 14.4 percent (ranging from 14.0 percent to 14.8 percent), equating to 14.3 million people aged 15-64 years who have used a psychoactive substance in the past year for non-medical reasons. Among every four drug users in Nigeria, one is a woman (UNODC, 2021). A greater number of men (annual prevalence of 21.8 percent or 10.8 million men) compared to women (annual prevalence of 7.0 percent or 3.4 million women) reported drug use in the past year in Nigeria. The highest rates of past-year drug use were observed in individuals aged 25-39 years (UNODC, 2019). Nearly a quarter of high-risk drug users had been apprehended for a drug-related offence during their drug use, with the majority (73 percent) arrested for drug possession; many high-risk drug users were also arrested for theft (12 percent), sex work (5 percent), burglary (4 percent), and shoplifting (2 percent) (UNODC, 2018).

Njuho and Davids (2010) noted that drug abuse is a growing issue in wealthy societies, incurring significant social and economic costs due to its effects on crime and health. They contend that the widespread use of illegal drugs fosters an unproductive society, heightens crime rates and mortality, thereby posing a substantial threat to the nation. For instance, South Africa, which has the highest number of individuals living with HIV, also ranks among the countries with the highest alcohol consumption levels (UNAIDS, 2007). Parry (2005) pointed out that alcohol, being the most consumed substance in the nation, is linked to numerous risky sexual behaviours that can facilitate the transmission of diseases such as HIV and AIDS.

Crime is defined as any action or failure to act by an individual within a group, community, or nation that contravenes established regulations, with specific penalties associated. It can also be viewed as an infringement against societal values (Omotor, 2009). "Crime, by its very nature, presents challenges globally, particularly in urban areas where it can influence residents' lifestyles and perspectives" (Inoma-Abbey and Kakulu, 2018). Nigeria, as a developing nation, is currently experiencing a rise in criminal activities and various forms of delinquency, including armed robbery, murder, rape, car theft, burglary, fraud, bribery and corruption, gambling, kidnapping, drug trafficking, money laundering, advanced fee fraud, cybercrime, and other unlawful acts (Adebayo, 2013; Modo, 2019).

Understanding the interplay between drug abuse and crime in the South-South region is crucial for tackling these intricate issues. A thorough investigation into the prevalence, trends, socioeconomic influences, health repercussions, and law enforcement difficulties related to drug abuse and crime is essential. By acquiring knowledge about the fundamental causes and effects, policymakers, law enforcement bodies, healthcare professionals, communities, and families can formulate evidence-based strategies and interventions to effectively address drug abuse and its associated criminal activities.

Nevertheless, despite acknowledging the issue, there is a significant deficiency in comprehensive research and data specifically concerning the local Schnapp (Ogogoro) produced by various families in the South-South region, particularly in Akwa Ibom State. This lack of information obstructs the formulation of targeted policies, prevention initiatives, and treatment services required to tackle the complex nature of drug abuse and its repercussions on crime. Consequently, it is imperative to conduct a study that examines the extent, patterns, and underlying factors of drug abuse within family units and their correlation

with crime in Akwa Ibom State of the South-South region.

The objective of this study is to fill the existing knowledge gaps and offer a thorough understanding of the occurrences of drug abuse and criminal activities in Akwa Ibom State of the South-South region. The results will provide a basis for evidence-based policies, strategies, and interventions that can enhance public health, improve law enforcement efforts, and strengthen community resilience by addressing the root causes and effects of drug abuse and crime. It is on this basis that this study investigates the prevalence of drug abuse and crime in the South-South region, using Akwa Ibom State as a case study.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the acknowledgement of the issue and the negative consequences associated with the abuse of substances such as tobacco, alcohol, cannabis, amphetamines, cocaine, and heroin, there remains a significant deficiency in knowledge and research regarding the abuse of local schnapp (Ogogoro). This beverage, which is produced locally, has a connection to the increasing crime rate in Akwa Ibom State and the broader South-South region. The oversight in researching Ogogoro, which is consumed during festivals, funerals, marriage celebrations, and by drivers in parks, represents a critical research gap that needs to be addressed. The insights gained from this research could enhance the existing data on substance abuse, potentially leading to the formulation of targeted policies and the establishment of prevention and treatment programs essential for addressing the complex nature of drug abuse and its influence on crime in Akwa Ibom State.

There is an urgent need to address the theoretical research gaps arising from the lack of accurate and up-to-date data regarding the prevalence of drug abuse in the region. This includes understanding the types of drugs commonly abused, the demographics of those who misuse drugs, and the patterns of drug abuse within Akwa Ibom State in the South-South region. Gaining a thorough understanding of the extent and prevalence of drug abuse is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies. Analysing factors such as unemployment, poverty, a lack of educational opportunities, and social exclusion can provide valuable insights into the underlying causes of drug abuse and how it exacerbates criminal behaviour. Addressing these concerns is crucial for strategic interventions aimed at combating drug abuse and its relationship with crime in Akwa Ibom State of the South-South region.

Objective of the study

This study is posed to examine the prevalence of drug abuse and related crimes in Akwa Ibom State, south-south region of Nigeria.

Review of related literature

The Concept of Drug Abuse

A Drug can be seen as substance taken by an individual which is capable of altering his or her biological operation. It is mostly used to refer to any stuff used for reason of relaxation or as an abused substance (Modester, 2016). Also, in pharmacology, a drug is a chemical compound that is utilized in handling, healing, averting sickness as well as improving physical and psychological welfare of an individual (Dorwick and Maline, 2007). We have

drugs that are psychoactive which are organic compound and can influence the operation of the nervous system, modifying sensitivity, temperament and cognizance. There are recreational drugs that are not used for reason of therapeutic but for fun, they are: alcohol, nicotine and caffeine, in addition to supplementary drugs like opiates and amphetamines. In addition, there are drugs that serve as food supplements such as vitamin, they are mostly prescribed by doctors and they are also useful in handling illness (Caulkins, 2013).

Drugs are dangerous and damaging when taken incorrectly. Hence, drug abuse occurs when a drug is consumed to stimulate physiological and mental impact for a reason other than healing purpose (Elizabeth, & Martin, 2007). It is an ingestion of mind modifying drugs like the tobacco, Indian hemp, cocaine, morphine, Heroin, Alcohol, ephedrine, Madras, Caffeine, Glue, Barbiturates, and Amphetamines and can be seen as a damaging utilization of legally prescribed drugs (Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole, 2010). Drug abuse refers to indiscriminate over- reliance or misapplication of a certain drug or short of a prior remedial result from competent doctors (Oluremi, 2012). Benjamin and Chide (2014) refer to drug abuse as the usage of drugs that is not largely approved on health grounds, which if these drugs are used regularly, it can alter temperament, behaviours and cause addiction.

Health grades staff editorial (2021) described drug abuse as the usage of unlawful medications or the consumption of prescribed medications in manner other than the way it was approved. Universally and locally, drug and substance abuse is an escalating challenge that pose danger with damaging impact on individuals 'wellbeing, safety, economic and socio-cultural welfare. Currently, drug and substance abuse has been identified as one of the habits destroying lives of people especially the teenagers, youths and even cut across the whole population of the world. Interesting, there is no nation that is exempted from the damaging impact of this act (Giade, 2012). World Drug Report presented by UNODC (2023) estimates that more than 13 million people are injecting drugs, 18 per cent higher than the previous estimation. Globally, close to 300 million people use drugs, this is a 23 per cent increase over the previous decade. The number of people with drug use disorders, have increased to close to 40 million globally, a 45 per cent increase over 10 years.

UNODC (2018) argued that Nigeria is not exempted from the issue of drug abuse. The challenge of drug abuse is wide spread among the young population which is a cause of concern to government, religious bodies, parents and the society at large. The spread of drug abuse in Nigeria is approximated at 14.4% or 14.3 million persons within the ages of 15 to 64 years, with its predominance way above in comparison to yearly world-wide predominance of any drug use of 5.6% amid adult population in 2016. Drug abuse is noted to usually result into over- reliance and obsession. The compulsive drug seeking behaviour usually leads to other antisocial behaviours such as crimes. Hence, the reason for the growing concern is as a result of the inclination of addicted individuals to engage in criminal activities and illegalities within the society. Activities such as organised crimes, cultism, ritual killings and insecurities usually thrive in solidarity with drug abuse (Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole, 2010). The WHO as well as the World Heart Foundation's data revealed that 22.1% of young ones between the ages of 12-17 consume tobacco in Nigeria (Giade, 2011). Ajibulu (2011) opined that instead of curbing this dangerous trend, drug abuse is enabled among young ones in Nigeria via advertisements, music, videos and movies that support its usage. This means, more young ones in Nigeria are likely to experiment with drugs and get addicted which is damaging to the

society and the country at large.

The Concept of Crime

Crime is a violation of the regulation of a country for which a constituted authority can approve a sentence. Crimes may lead to reprimands, therapy, imprisonment and even death. Every society has their own definition of what constitutes a crime and the punishment attached to the violation. The issue of crime is not limited to violation against a person, it is seen as violation against the society and it is not an issue between two individuals but a case between the violator and the state (Singh, 2021). It is an illicit act for which the violator is liable to be reprimanded at the instance of the state. It can also be seen as a doing or error entailing violation of obligation indictable by vested authority. It is a human behaviour that the government wants to eliminate through warning of indictment and legitimate arraignment (Isiaka and Okaphor, 2018). Crime is a socially destructive deed or error that breaks the value safeguarded by a country. In past times, the rate of crime was low but presently crime rate is at an all-time high, the reason for this exponential increase is traceable to various factors ranging from social, economic, psychological and environmental factors (Marchuk 2013).

There are certain components that make a wrong to be seen as a crime. Firstly, for a crime to occur, there must be “mens rea” (which means the individual must have the intention to commit the crime), “actus rea” which means the person(s) must carry out the act and lastly the wrong doing must be followed by a grievance or damage suffered by another person which may be bodily, psychological or monetary damage (Singh, 2021). Thotakura (2015), observed that crimes are committed in four levels which include intention, groundwork, preliminary and completion of crime. Hence, in the first phase, there must be intent to commit crime, afterwards, plans will be put in place for the commission of the intended crime which is the groundwork. Then, an attempt will be made to commit the crime which will lead to the last phase of committing the crime itself. Therefore, a person will only be liable for a crime when they are able to prove that his actions led to the crime in question.

The Kinds of crimes committed under influence of a drug.

Thotakura (2015) observed that the nature of crimes associated with drug use can be categorized into personal, property, organized crimes, juvenile delinquency and terrorism.

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Personal crimes - are crimes that aim at an individual, which may involve the following: assault (which has to do with unlawful attack on another person), domestic violence (which also includes assault), murder (which has to do with assassinating a person) and sexual assault (which is commonly known as rape). This was reiterated by Obiechina and Isiguzo, (2016) in their study which revealed that hallucinogens, narcotics and inhalants intake leads to violent conduct by the users. This is in line with another study that revealed that drug users show symptoms of addiction and are probably more ready to participate in violence (Kopak and Hoffman, 2014). Moreover, Payne and Gaffney (2012) asserted that consumers of methamphetamines regularly suffer from defects around the prefrontal cortex and amygdala area of the brain which consequence include: social disorder, touchiness, resentment and hostility. Drug use may lead to low cognitive and attitudinal management sanctioning uninhibited violence (Deza, 2012).

- ii. Property crimes are those crimes that is solely focused on material property, they include; Burglary (this has to do with an unlawful breaking or gaining access into another person's property with intent to steal from the property), Theft (this has to do with carting away something that is not your own without the use of force and without the notice or permission of the owner), Arson (this is the act of intentionally setting another person's property ablaze) and Vandalism (it is an act of destroying individual or government owned property). Obiechina and Isiguzo, (2016) opined that one of the attitudinal effects of stimulants is theft. Also, Hussein, Muktar and Umar (2017) admitted that property crimes can be linked to drug abuse. Meanwhile, Kuhn *et al* (2014) asserted that substance abusers are most likely to be detained over property crime, especially heroin addicts.
- iii. Organized crimes - are crimes committed by more than one person and it is usually carried out in a combined and cooperative style. These kind of crimes are kidnapping, selling of unlawful drugs, trafficking, money laundering, and so on. Thompson and Uggen, (2012) revealed that for a drug abuser to sustain his or her habit, he or she needs money, meanwhile, most drug abusers do not earn their money legally. One of the sure ways they earn their money is by involving in unlawful sale and distribution of drugs. Also, Bennett and Edwards (2016) agreed that even though it is possible for a drug user to possess lawful means of earning money, nonetheless, small proportion of drug users have lawful earnings, hence, drug users normally participate in illegal activities to sustain their habit via the sale of banned substances. When drug abusers get addicted to a particular drug or drugs, they will do anything to consistently have a supply of the drugs (Jakaza and Nyomi, 2018). In the aspect of organized crimes, Adeyemo *et al.* (2016) agreed that drug abuse leads to organized crimes and cult activities especially in academic institutions.
- iv. Juvenile delinquency - it is committed by people below the age of eighteen years. Jakaza and Nyoni (2018) opined that drug abuse by young ones will most likely lead to participation in more severe crime and drug abuse. They argued that young ones when introduced to drug, usually start participating in petty crimes like picking pockets but as time goes on, they may start engaging in severe and dangerous criminal activities, even their taste or choice of substances will also become more sophisticated and dangerous. Furthermore, a lot of criminals are drug users, and they took up the habit when they were young, then they continued with the habit till they became addicted and turned to a harden criminal (Thotakura, 2015). Oluwole *et al.* (2018) also agreed that drug abuse leads to juvenile delinquency as it serves as their entry point into criminal conduct.
- v. Terrorism – this is one of the probable criminal activities that emanate as a result of distribution and trade in drugs. Global trafficking of illegal drugs heightens terrorist activities via these medium: provision of money, establishing disorder and insecurity, backing dishonesty and offering protection and maintenance of shared structures for illegal undertakings and buying the loyalty of law enforcement authorities. Diverse drugs, diverse trafficking pathways and groups have diverse relatedness to risk of terrorism. Hence, these groups will try to get their way by focusing on law enforcement on their pathways by using any means to carry out their trades even by use of force and violence. Also, these drug dealers sometimes operate in sync by partnering with other

terror groups to carry out their trade, hence, there are claims that proceeds from drug trafficking are used to finance terrorism (UNODC, 2011).

Theoretical Framework

Strain Theory

Strain theory states that social structures within society may pressure citizens to commit crime. The theory states that certain strains or stresses increase the likelihood of crime. The strains lead to negative emotions such as frustration and anger. As the emotions create pressure and weigh heavily for corrective action; crime becomes one possible response. Strain theories have many proponents including Emile Durkheim, Robert K. Merton, Robert Agnew, Albert K Cohen, Richard Rosenfield and Jie Zhang. All these theorists agree that crime may be used to reduce or escape from strain, seek revenge against the source of strain or related targets or alleviate negative emotions (Agnew, 2014). For example, unemployed individuals may engage in theft drug selling to obtain money or take illicit drug to calm nerves.

The major versions of strain theory describe (a) the particular strains most likely to lead to crime (b) why strains increase crime and (c) the factors that lead a person to or dissuade a person from responding to strains with crime. All strain theories acknowledge that only a minority of strained individuals turn to crime (Agnew, 2014).

Emile Durkheim developed the first modern strain theory of crime (Durkheim 1951) but Merton's classic strain and its offshoots came to dominate criminology during the middle part of the 20th century (Merton 1949). Classic strain theory focuses on the type of strain involving the inability to achieve monetary success or the somewhat broader goal of middle class status. The classic strain theories fell into decline in 1970' and 1980' due to the challenges by current researches.

Robert Agnew developed his general strain theory (GST) in 1992, which has since become the leading version of the strain theory and one of the major theories of crime Agnew (1992) focuses on a broad range of strains, including the inability to achieve a variety of goals, the loss of valued possessions and negative treatment by others GST has been applied to a range of topics including the explanation of gender, race/ethnicity, age, community and societal differences in crime rates. It has also been applied to many types of crimes and deviance, including corporate crime, police deviance, bullying suicide, terrorism and eating disorders. Much evidence also suggests that the strains identified by GST increase the likelihood of crime, although the predictions of GST about the types of people most likely to respond to these strains with crime may have received less support but cannot be ignored.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design. Descriptive research design was applied to ensure accuracy and thorough description of the properties or characteristics of the problem under study. This is motivated by the position of Isangedihi *et al.*, (2004), which holds that the descriptive design allows orderly collection of data. The study area was Akwa Ibom state. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria, created on the 23rd of September 1987, with Uyo as its capital. Akwa Ibom is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with a population of 7, 200,000 as at 2023 (aks.gov.ng, 2024). According to the Akwa Ibom State government official website, the

projected estimation of Akwa Ibom State population is 7,200,000 (aks.gov.ng, 2024). The population is said to be estimated based on an annual growth rate of 3.4%. Akwa Ibom State's economy is based on the production of crude oil and natural gas. It is indeed one of the foremost producers of crude oil among other States in Nigeria. Its oil producing local government areas are Ibeno, Mbo, Eastern Obolo (Usoro, 2010). The work employs Cochran (1977) sampling technique to determine the sample size out of the population of 7,200,000 in Akwa Ibom State. A 95% confidence level and level of maximum variability (P= 0.5) was assumed. Where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and E is the level of precision (allowable error) that is 3% or 0.03

$$\frac{N \times Z^2 \times P(1 - P)}{(E^2 \times (N - 1) + Z^2 \times P \times (1 - P))}$$

Where N=Population size(7,200,000)

Z= confidence level 95%

P= Estimated proportion (If known use 0.5 for Maximum variability)

E= marginal error 3%(0.03)

$$= \frac{7,200,000 \times (1.96)^2 \times (0.5) \times (1 - 0.5)}{(0.03)^2 \times (7,200,000 - 1) + (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 + (1 - 0.5)}$$

$$= \frac{7,200,000 \times 3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0009 \times 7,199,999 + 3.8416 + 0.25}$$

$$= \frac{6,931,200}{6,479,991 + 0.9604}$$

$$= \frac{6,931,200}{6,480.9595}$$

$$= 1,069$$

There are three senatorial districts in Akwa Ibom North-East (Uyo), Akwa Ibom North-west (Ikot Ekpene) and Akwa Ibom South (Eket). Two (Eket and Uyo) out of the three Senatorial districts will be purposively selected for this study. Uyo and Eket Senatorial district will be selected for this study for the following reasons. Uyo is the capital of Akwa Ibom State, it also has the Nigerian Correction Service and the office of National Drug and Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) and close proximity to a pool of research assistants from the University of Uyo and with the establishments of drinking joints located in almost every corner, street of the capital. Eket senatorial district will be selected because of the beehive of activity in the district and the Nigerian Correction Service. Also, unlike Ikot Ekpene, Eket is quite far from Uyo and will guarantee an independent findings from what will be gathered in Uyo.

The Study participants will be classified into class A and class B. The Staff of NDLEA and the Nigerian Correction Service in Uyo and Eket will be under class A, while the populace of Uyo and Eket senatorial district will be under class B.

Data for this study was collected by the researcher who was be assisted by three (3) trained research assistants. The respondents were met in purposively selected hotspots

around Uyo and Eket metropolis, locations like selected bars, Liquor stores, hotels, carparks, etc. To collect the needed data, the researcher and the research assistants, first disclosed the objectives of the study to the respondents and requested their candid responses. For the respondents who were interviewed, the questions were asked in English for the class A participants and the questionnaire were distributed to respondents purposively. The research assistants were trained on the objective and design of the study. The data collected through questionnaire in this study were presented using the percentage method and analysed using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results

Prevalence of Drug Abuse in Akwa Ibom State

Investigating the prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State requires insight into the availability of drugs, accessibility of drugs and the cultural indices that influence drug abuse among the people of Akwa Ibom State. The first contains a descriptive presentation of the frequency of opinions of the study respondents on the prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State, while the latter presents the qualitative analysis from interviews with excerpts.

Table 1: *Distribution of study respondents on the prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State*

There is a prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	506	50.4	50.4	50.4
Agreed	490	48.9	48.9	99.3
Valid Strongly Disagreed	6	.6	.6	99.9
Disagreed	1	.1	.1	100.0
Total	1003	100.0	100.0	

Information in Table 5.1 shows the responses of respondents on the prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State. 506 (50.4%) of the study respondents strongly agreed that drug abuse is prevalent in the state. A total of 490 (48.9%) of the study respondents agreed that on the prevalence of drug abuse in the state as compare to 6 (6%) who strongly disagreed and 1 (1%) who disagreed on the prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State. The analysis of Table 5.1 shows that there is a high prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State.

On the same subject matter, all the participants interviewed in the study believed that drug abuse is prevalent in Akwa Ibom State. One of the key informants who was interviewed reported that there high level of drug abuse in the state. In his narratives, he reported that:

Yes, drug abuse is prevalent among the people of Akwa Ibom State, especially among the young ones. We in Akwa Ibom State have a culture that promotes drug abuse because there are many traditional practices like our traditional marriage ceremony and burial ceremonies. These traditional practices promote drug abuse

because of the substances we collect for the youths as their right of consumption during these ceremonies. I must tell you that cigarettes, raw tobacco, ogogoro or as we call it, ufofop, and other spirits are normally collected for the youths by the elders as the youths' items, and all of these substances are substances that can intoxicate. So, these practices contribute to the prevalence of drug abuse in the state (**Deputy in-charge, 50 years, male, Correctional Centre, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State**).

Another study participant in his narratives confirmed that drug abuse is prevalent in Akwa Ibom State. In his narrative, he reported that:

The people here, especially the youths in this state, abuse different drugs like marijuana, cocaine, and various alcoholic drinks. So, drug abuse is prevalent here in this state. You will see young people engaging in these acts of drug sales and drug abuse. The rate of drug abuse is so high in this state that the spread is across rural areas to the urban centres (**Senior Officer, 49 years, males, Correctional Centre, Eket, Akwa Ibom State**).

A participant from the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) in his narrative agreed that there is prevalence of drug abuse among the young people of Akwa Ibom State. He reported that:

Although in our practice, we do not focus on those psychoactive items considered to be part the cultural item like Ogogoro, snuff and other forms of tobacco as consume and abuse by the people for their traditional activates, we concentrate on the hard drugs like cocaine, marijuana, codeine, etc, but I can say vividly that there is prevalence of drug abuse among the people, both elders and youths are into the abuse of drugs (**Officer, 45 years, male, NDLEA, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State**).

Discussion of Findings

Drug abuse has been discovered to be part of the culture of Akwa Ibom people through traditional practices through which they accept Ogogoro, different forms of tobacco like snuff, raw tobacco leaves and cigarette and part of traditional marriage requirement. Abuse of drugs is prevalence in the state across males and females, young people and the elderly. Girls has been part of the crime of selling drugs in the state and some of them are now inmates in the state's correctional centres. Local brew with Ogogoro in combination of marijuana, cocaine, palm wine, lemon grass and yoghourt called "*brew*" is abused in traditional events of the people of Akwa Ibom State. This agrees with the UNDOC (2011) report, that past year prevalence of any drug use is estimated at 14.4 per cent (range 14.0 per cent - 14.8 per cent), corresponding to 14.3 million people aged 15-64 years who had used a psychoactive substance in the past year for non- medical purposes and UNDOC (2018) report, that nearly one quarter of high-risk drug users had been arrested for a drug-related offence during the

course of their drug use, while the majority (73 per cent) had been arrested for possession of drugs, many high-risk drug users had also been arrested for theft (12 per cent), sex work (5 per cent), burglary (4 per cent) and shoplifting 2 (per cent).

The study found correlations in quantitative and qualitative reports on the prevalence of drug abuse in Akwa Ibom State. For instance, information obtained through the questionnaire indicates that drugs like marijuana, cocaine, codeine, ogogoro and others are abused by the people of the state. Qualitative data gathered from officers of the Correctional Centres in Uyo and Eket, and officers of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) Uyo, also revealed that abuse of drug is prevalence with drugs like marijuana (Indian hemp), cocaine, ogogoro, codeine and other cough syrup.

Drug abuse and drug trafficking cases in Nigeria have gained massive notoriety within and outside the country, topping the list as the highest drug using nation in West Africa, and accounting for about 14% of drug use prevalence, which is higher than the global average (UNODC, 2021; NDCMP, 2015-2019). The South-South region, known for its rich natural resources and economic activities, has witnessed a significant rise in the prevalence of drug abuse over the years, with over 2 million people estimated to have used a drug (UNODC, 2018). The availability of drugs have been a key determinant to drug abuse among the people in. However, in the case of Akwa Ibom State, traditions and cultural practices of the people have created avenue for constant availability of drugs. Substance like ogogoro has been abused by the people as part of traditions in most of their cultural activities. This substance and marijuana, and in their combination has been abused by the people of the state and the prevalence of the abuse is enhance by traditional acceptability of the substance.

Conclusion

Drug has been a known determinant of crime all over the world. In Akwa Ibom State, drug abuse has been a causal factor for crimes committed in the state. There is a prevalence of drug abuse related crimes in Akwa Ibom State. This has been as a result of accessibility through availability of drugs as provided by the traditional practices of the people. Substances like ogogoro, and other alcoholic drinks which are not considered as drugs by the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) has been a causal factor for many crimes committed in Akwa Ibom State. Abuse of drug is seen as part of the norm due to the traditional acceptability of psychoactive substances as youths' items of the youths during traditional events among the people of Akwa Ibom State.

References

- Adebayo A. A. (2013) Social Factors Affecting Effective Crime Prevention and Control in Nigeria *International Journal of Applied Sociology* 2013, 3(4): 71-75
- Beauchamp, T. L and Childress, J. F. 2019. Principles of Biomedical Ethics. Oxford Univeristy Press(OUP)
- Carter, Ethon, World, Tony and Strauss-Hughes (2020). The Classificatin of Crime and its Related Problems. A Pluralistic Approach.
- Cohran W.G. (11977) Sampling Techniques. 3rd Edition Wiley.
- Dorwick, F.O., & Maline, E. (2007). Principle for drug education. *Journal of Public Health*, 23 (4), 295-300

- Inoma-Abbey O. I. & Kakulu I. I. (2018). Appraising The Effect of Variation in Crime on Property Values in Port Harcourt, Nigeria *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* Vol. 7 pg67-74
- Modo, P. I. (2019). A Close Examination of Cybercriminals in Nigeria *South South Journal of Culture and Development* Vol. 21 (1) April
- Njuho P. & Davids A. (2010). Extent and Influence of Recreational Drug Use on Men and Women Aged 15years and older in South Africa *African Journal of Drug & Alcohol Studies*, 9(1), 2010
- Omotor G. Douglasson (2009). Socio-Economic Determinants of Crime in Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* 6(2): 54-59.
- UNAIDS, (2007):Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS. Report on the Global AIDS epidemic. Geneva: UNAIDS
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2018) *Drug Use in Nigeria* https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/statistics/Drugs/Drug_Use_Survey_Nigeria_2019_BOOK.pdf Accessed April, 2020
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2021). World drug report 2021. Available at: <https://wdr.unodc.org/wdr2019/en/exsum.html> (Accessed 08 18, 2021).
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2023) <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/press/releases/2023/June/unodc-world-drug-report-2023-warns-of-converging-crises-as-illicit-drug-markets-continue-to-expand.html>
- Usoro, E. J. (2010) Geology. In Usoro, E. J. and Akpan, A. A. (eds) Akwa Ibom State; a Geological perspective. A publication of the Department of Geology and Regional Planning. University of Uyo.
- Njuho P. & Davids A. (2010). Extent and Influence of Recreational Drug Use on Men and Women Aged 15years and older in South Africa *African Journal of Drug & Alcohol Studies*, 9(1), 2010
- Omotor G. D. (2009). Socio-Economic Determinants of Crime in Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* 6(2): 54-59.
- Obiechina, G. O. & Isiguzo, B.C. (2016). Curbing the Menace of Drug use Among Secondary School Students in Nigeria. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol. 4 No. 1, 2016 ISSN 2056-5852
- Parry C. D. H. (2005). A review of policy-relevant strategies and interventions to address the burden of alcohol on individuals and society in South Africa. *South African Psychiatry Review*, 8, 20-24.
- Sarker, S. K. & Faller, E. (2016). An exploratory framework of drug related crime in forensic sciences and criminology. *Malysian Applied Biology Journal* 45.
- UNAIDS, (2007):Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS. Report on the Global AIDS epidemic. Geneva
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2018) *Drug Use in Nigeria* https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/statistics/Drugs/Drug_Use_Survey_Nigeria_2019_BOOK.pdf Accessed April, 2020
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2021). World drug report 2021.

Available at: <https://wdr.unodc.org/wdr2019/en/exsum.html> (Accessed 08 18, 2024). United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2023)

